

AWD Irrigation Techniques in Rice Paddy Irrigation: A Great Opportunity for Bangladesh

Md Rahedul Islam and Wataru Takeuchi

Institute of Industrial Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

Corresponded Authors Email: rahe@iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp

Abstract: *Alternate wetting and drying irrigation techniques is an irrigation process which allows the paddy crops field dry and wet alternatively for a certain period instead of continuously flooded. By AWD irrigation practices, the less irrigation water required as well as the methane emission reduced without yield variation. Bangladesh is selected as study area due to the 4th largest rice production country and the area under irrigation drastically increased. The main objective of the study is to find out the possible feedback on AWD irrigation practices in Bangladesh. The secondary data from published journal, books, Bangladesh agricultural statistical yearbook, Agricultural census report, BRRRI, BARC, MoA and MoP reports are used. The methodology applied for this study are- (i) to review numbers of published journal article, report and statistics for the existing AWD practices result in Bangladesh; (ii) trend analysis of irrigated area, rice production, equipment of irrigation, cost of irrigation and energy used from 1980-2016, and (iii) finally, calculated the benefits of AWD irrigation compared with non-AWD irrigation by using data envelopment analysis. The result shows that the AWD irrigation has 20% more economic benefit than non-AWD irrigation and as a surplus 40% less methane emission.*

Key words: *AWD, Data envelopment analysis, Benefit, Bangladesh*

1.Introduction: Rice is the staple food for more of the half of world population and rice production sector is the largest consumers of irrational water (GRiSP,2013). Bangladesh is the agriculture dominant country and 70% of the territory dominant by agriculture land (World Bank, 2014). Bangladesh is the 4th largest per head rice consuming and rice producing country in the world (FAO, 2015). The rice is the dominant crop of the country and it covers three-fourths of all cropland area and contributes 70% of calories consumed (Majumder et al. 2016. The country population is almost 170 million and expected to be 210 million in 2050 (UN, 2015). Due to the drastic population growth, the country demanded more rice production in future. But the arable land area of the country is even decreasing over time due to increasing demand for residential and industrial use (Hasan et al., 2013). Bangladesh also suffers from periodic natural calamities such as drought, flooding, and cyclones. Due to its location in a delta, climate change and associated sea level rise is expected to increase the risk for flooding and salinization of agricultural lands, especially near the southern coast (Hossain and Silva, 2013; MOA-FAO, 2012). As a result, farmers are cultivating the rice paddy more intensively with using the irrigation and fertilizer with continuous flooding system. Due to the excessive pumping of groundwater for irrigation, the water table declined day by day and rice field are becomes a major source of methane emission. To produce more rice with less water and methane emission alternative wetting

and drying technology is a useful tool. In 2002, International rice research institute introduce a set of guidelines coupled with an easy-to-use and practical tool to allow farmers to reduce irrigation water use without losing yield. This form of “safe” AWD is now recommended practice in many countries or regions, including Bangladesh (Palis et al., 2014), the Philippines (Rejesus et al., 2013; Lampayan et al., 2014b), Myanmar (Lampayan et al., 2014b), and Vietnam (Rejesus et al., 2013). This study will investigate the opportunities of AWD application in Bangladesh rice cultivation on the perspective of climate change and socio-economic perspective.

2. Background of the study: The rice production covers 75% of total cropland area and 80% of the total irrigated area in the country (IRRI, 2010). Rice is the 60% of total crop agriculture and contributes 18% for the gross domestic product of the country (GoB, 2015). In addition, the lives and livelihoods of about 13 million farm households and approximately 50 percent of the workforce, who are engaged in agriculture primarily, depend on rice production (BBS, 2010). The water use for agriculture becoming scarce (Rijsberman, 2006) and costly due to the groundwater declination and competition with non-agricultural sector water uses. In Bangladesh, about 70% of the fresh water is diverted to irrigate rice land. It has been estimated that 3000-5000 litres of water is required to produce 1.0 kg of rice (SAIC, 2007). In Bangladesh, farmers are habituated to maintain continuous standing water in rice land, which is associated with increased energy consumption and eventually higher cost of production. In fact, 20-30% of the rice production cost is incurred for irrigation only in case of irrigated rice depending on soil type and mode of payment (Alam, 2006). There are three main ecotypes of rice; Aus season, March to August; Aman season, June to November; and Boro season, December to May (BBS, 2012). The main rice production season Boro is fully depended on irrigation and due to the rainfall pattern change Aus rice also going to be the almost irrigated season. The Aman season is still now rainfed and irrigated season. Due to the high yield rate, Boro season is the main rice producing season in the country and its fully depended on irrigation. The irrigated Boro rice area of the country increased almost 20 times from 1975 to 2015 (BBS, 2016). Currently, 35,322 deep tube wells, 1,523,322 shallow tube wells and 170,570 low lift pumps are working in Bangladesh to provide water for irrigation. About 79% of the total cultivated area in Bangladesh is irrigated by groundwater, whereas the remaining is irrigated by surface water (Qureshi, A.S., et al., 2014). The groundwater table declined 30 meters from 8 meters in 1974 in some area of the north-western part of Bangladesh. Moreover, Irrigated Boro rice accounts for more than a third of the total agricultural emissions in Bangladesh (excluding land use change and forestry) (FAOSTAT 2016). Bangladesh submitted an Intended Nationally Determined Contribution (INDC) to the UNFCCC’s Paris Agreement in September 2015. Though agriculture is not included in the unconditional commitments, the report specifies potential actions in livestock, fertilizer usage, and rice cultivation. To improving water use efficiencies through the adoption of resource-conserving crop management practices such as alternate wetting and drying (AWD), direct-seeded rice, and bed planting could help in reducing groundwater demand for agriculture. Among this AWD technology is most effective and user-friendly for the farmers. Alternative water-saving irrigation techniques have been developed and increasingly adopted in rice growing countries during recent decades. The aims of this paper are to overview the opportunities and

advantages of water-saving irrigation technology with particular reference to alternate wetting and drying irrigation in rice cultivation.

3.Study Area: Bangladesh is being select as the study area. Bangladesh is a small country with 1,47,570 sqkm areas with 170 million people. The physically of Bangladesh is mostly low land alluvial deposited country with the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna rivers is the largest deltas in the world (Ahmad et al. 2001). The country located at the lowermost reaches of G-B-M rivers system which drain 1.72 sq.km of land. Along with 230 rivers flow through the country like a complex network. The rivers are played very important rules in the culture, agriculture, transportation and livelihood of the countryman. But most recently due to the climate change and human intervention, the upper flow of the river decreased and most of the small river are dried up and the large river are also dried up and creates a lot of sandbars. As a result, the surface water flow and water reservoir of country decreased a lot. Conversely, groundwater irrigation has increased dramatically over the last three decades. The availability of surface water is not consistent because of seasonal variation. Ninety-five percent of the surface water in the river system also originates outside the country (Ahmad et al. 2001). This introduces uncertainty in surface water availability. For example, the availability of surface water in 1990 ranged from 3710 Mm³ during the dry season to 111,250 Mm³ during the wet season (BBS, 2013). Bangladesh experiences a tropical monsoon climate with significant variations in rainfall and temperature. Average annual rainfall varies from 1,200 mm in the extreme west to over 4,000mm in the northeast (Chowdhury 2010). About 80% of all rainfall occurs during the monsoon from June to September (Figure 3). In the post-monsoon (October November) and winter period (December–February), only 20% of the annual rainfall is available. Therefore there is a seasonal water shortage depending on the duration of the monsoon. The map of the study arena is shown in fig-3.1.

Fig-3.1: Study area with rice cultivated area

4.Objectives of the study: The main objectives of the study to investigate the advantages of Alternative wetting and drying irrigation system in Bangladesh. Within the research questions, Is AWD irrigation system is benefited for Bangladesh? Why should Bangladesh adopt AWD irrigation system? AWD irrigations basics guidelines input and output has been analyzed to investigate the main research objective.

5.Materials and Methodology: The study used both quantities and qualitative approaches for the objectives of the study. To solve the research questions and achieves the goal, the literature review, data collection and analysis are the main stages of this study. The published research papers, reports and working paper on Bangladesh AWD irrigation system has been reviewed. The secondary data have been collected from the Bangladesh Agricultural Statistical Yearbook, Department of Agriculture Extension, FAOSTAT, USAID, BIRRI, IRRI, and published research paper. The primary data used as a sharing experience of the AWD irrigation practiced farmer of Bangladesh. The data are analysis with some simple statistical application and represents with table, graph and diagram.

6.Irrigated Rice Production in Bangladesh: Rice is the staple food of Bangladesh and accounting for about 75% of land use, 28% of national GDP and source of income of 39% people. The rice production must be increased 45 MT in 2050 from 34 MT in 2016 (Kabir, et. Al, 2015). The rice production practices are still labor intensive and low profitable. Due to the adverse impacts of climate change especially the rainfall pattern and temperature pattern changes, the rice cultivation is now almost irrigation depended. The Boro rice is the main rice production season in dry December to April month and totally irrigated especially ground water irrigation. The Aus and Amon are produces in rainy season but not its also need the supplementary or fully irrigation. The country need to produce 70% more food in 2050 for the enlarged population (FAO, 2012. According to MoEF (2010), rice production in Bangladesh is expected to further increase from 30.7 million tones in 2007 to 35.4 million tons in 2015 and 36.8 million tons in 2021 respectively. In figure 6.1(a) and (b) shows the historical trend of rice production, consumption and irrigated areas.

Source: BARC, BBS 1980-2014

7.Environmental Impacts of Rice Production: Bangladesh is one of the most climate change risk vulnerable country. To meet up the food demand of extended population, the country need to produces more rice. Consequently, to produce more rice, its need to pumping more ground water. The country is already facing great challenges to ground water stability. The ground water table declined significantly each and every year (Fig. 7.1 and 7.2). Moreover, the flooded rice paddy is one of the largest sources of methane emissions. A Methane molecule has 35 times the direct global warming potential of a molecule of carbon dioxides. In Bangladesh, Agriculture is the leading contributor, with 39% of total emissions coming from the agriculture sub-sector activities (Fig. X) and rice paddy is the largest one, almost 39% (FAOSTAT, 2015). In 2015, the per capita GHG emission was 6.76 tCO₂ which will be increased up to 82% in 2025BaU.

Sources: (7.1) BBS, BWDA 1980-2011; (7.2) *WRI CAIT 2.0, 2015; FAOSTAT, 2015*

8.AWD irrigation Technology: Alternate wetting and drying (AWD) is one of the most recent advances in rice irrigation water management. Generally, rice is cultivated under continuous flooding in the rice field. In AWD irrigation, rice field allowed to dry for a certain period and re-flooded again instead of continuous flooded. The period of watered-dry-rewatered depend on the weather, soil types, land types and other characteristics and varied from 3-10 days. Save AWD irrigation, after 10-15 days of transplanting to flowering the rice field watered 15 cm above the surface and the water allowed to decreased 15 cm below the surface layer. AWD irrigation techniques are water management system and no need the extra investment, just using a

perforated plastic or bamboo pipe is used to measure the soil surface water layers. In fig-8.1 and 8.2 shows the common water cycle and tool for AWD adaptation. Moreover, By AWD irrigation practices, the rice production is increased 5-15% and due to the field dryness the methane emission also decreased 40-70% and water save from 30 to 60% (J, Yang (2016), B. A. liquist, (2015), and paul, et al. (2013). The benefit of AWD irrigation practices shows in table-X. In Bangladesh, it is being promoted by the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), the Rural Development Academy (RDA), the Department of Agriculture Extension (DAE) in 2005. As a Wetting and Drying (AWD) is a water-saving technology that farmers can apply to reduce their irrigation water consumption in rice fields without decreasing its yield. By saving water use also can save the precious groundwater and energy consumption and as well as the environment.

Sources: AWD practiced farmer's experience

9.AWD irrigation and opportunity for Bangladesh: AWD irrigation techniques have been introduced in Bangladesh in 2005 but still, now only 5% of farmers used it. The studies show (Table: 2) that the alternate wetting and drying techniques are reducing the environmental impacts without production loss. To faces the two great challenges for the country; to produce the more food for the growing population and to face the environmental adverse impacts of rice production by using AWD irrigation technologies. Although, some research shows the AWD irrigation producing nitrous oxides and needs more weeding cost. But, in term of benefit, these disadvantages are negotiable.

Benefited items	Save AWD to Non-AWD
Gain Yield	5.6 to 12.8 %
Irrigation Water	-22.4 to -34.6%
WUE (GY/IW)	27.3 to 55.7%
CH ₄ Emission	-51.4 to -72.5 %
N ₂ O Emission	15.5 to 98.6 %
Global warming potential (GWP)	-48.6 to -67.2
GHG index (GWP/grain yield)	-48.3 to -78.9

Alternate wetting and	
Water Use	30-60%
Production	5-15%
Methane E	40-70%

Fig-9.1: Benefit of AWD irrigation techniques	Fig-9.2: Benefit of AWD irrigation
---	------------------------------------

Sources: Prince, et al. (2013), M. Shahe, Alam,(2009), J, Yang (2016), B. A. liquist, (2015), paul, et al. (2013), H., Zhang, (2008), BRKB, (2010)

10.Conclusion: AWD irrigation have creates a new opportunities for Bangladesh. The dilemma of rice production and environmental impacts could be solved practicing AWD irrigation. Although, the Govt. institutions are trying to adopted AWD irrigation technology but still not widely used technology in Bangladesh. The government organizations, NGO's, academician and the stakeholder should sit together and find the way to uses AWD irrigation in field level. This study recommended setting out the better AWD adoption strategies for irrigation in Bangladesh.

References

- Adam H. Price, Gareth J. Norton, David E. Salt, Oliver Ebenhoeh, Andrew A. Meharg, Caroline Meharg, M. Rafiqul Islam, Ramen N. Sarma, Tapash Dasgupta, Abdelbagi M. Ismail, Kenneth L. McNally, Hao Zhang, Ian C. Dodd & William J. Davies, (2014), Alternate wetting and drying irrigation for rice in Bangladesh: Is it sustainable and has plant breeding something to offer?, *Food and Energy Security*, 2013; 2(2):120–129, *doi: 10.1002/fes3.29*
- Ahmad, M. D., Kirby, M., Islam, M. S., Hossain, M. J., & Islam, M. M. (2014). Groundwater use for irrigation and its productivity: status and opportunities for crop intensification to achieve food security in Bangladesh. *Water Resources Management*, 28, 1415–1429. *doi:10. 1007/s11269-014-0560-z.*
- Alam, M. Shahe, M. S. Islam, M. A. Salam and M. A. Islam, 2009. Economics of Alternate Wetting and Drying Method of Irrigation: Evidences from farm level study, *The Agriculturists* 7(1&2): 128-136 (2009) ISSN-1729-5211, *A Scientific Journal of Krishi Foundation.*
- B.A. Linquist, M.M. Anders, M.A.A. Adviento-Borbe, R.L. Chaney, L.L. Nalley, E.F.F. Da Rosa, C. Van Kessel, Reducing greenhouse gas emissions, water use, and grain arsenic levels in rice systems, *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 21 (2015) 407–417.
- BADC (Bangladesh Agricultural Development Corporation), 2013. *Minor irrigation survey report 2012-2013.* Bangladesh Agricultural Development Corporation, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of Bangladesh.

BBS, (2012), *Agricultural Statistical Yearbook of Bangladesh*, GoB, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 1980-2012

BBS, *Agricultural Statistical Year Book of Bangladesh*, GoB, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2010-15.

BBS. (2010). Statistical yearbook of Bangladesh 2009. Dhaka: Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. BBS. (1980-2012).

FAO, IFAD and WFP. (2013). The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2013. The multiple dimensions of food security. *Rome: Food and Agricultural Organization*.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Statistics Division (FAOSTAT), viewed October 16, 2015: http://faostat3.fao.org/browse/area/*/E.

Jiang, Z., Huete, A.R., Didan, K., Miura, T., 2008. Development of a two-band enhanced vegetation index without a blue band. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 112, 3833–3845.

GoB, *Bangladesh Economic Review*, Bangladesh Ministry of Finance, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 1975-2015.

GRiSP (Global Rice Science Partnership), 2013. Rice Almanac, fourth ed. Inter-national Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines, pp. 283, Web site: www.cgiar.org/rice-grisp

H. Zhang, S.F. Zhang, J.C. Yang, J.H. Zhang, Z.Q. Wang, Postanthesis moderate wetting drying improves both quality and quantity of rice yield, *Agron. J.* 100 (2008) 726–734.

Hassan, A., Wahid, S., Shrestha, M. L., Rashid, M. A., Ahmed, T., Mazumder, A., Sarker, M. H., Al Hossain, B. M. T., Mumu, S., & Sarker, M. H. (2014). Climate change and water availability in the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna Basin: impact on local crop production and policy directives. In R. A. Vaidya & E. Sharma (Eds.), *Research insights on climate and water in the Hindu Kush Himalayas* (pp. 97–108). Kathmandu: ICIMOD.

IRRI, International Rice Research Institute, 2010, Manila, Phillipine.

Jianchang Yang, Qun Zhou, Jianhua Zhang, (2016), Moderate wetting and drying increases rice yield and reduces water use, grain arsenic level, and methane emission, *Crop Science Society of China and Institute of Crop Science, CAAS. Production and hosting by Elsevier B.V.* This is an open access article under the CC BY-NC-ND license, (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>).

Roderick M. Rejesus, Florencia G. Palis, Divina Gracia P. Rodriguez, Ruben M. Lampayan, Bas A.M. Bouman, (2010), Impact of the alternate wetting and drying (AWD) water-saving irrigation technique: Evidence from rice producers in the Philippines, *Field Crops Research* 170 (2015) 95–108, Elsevier publications, Food Policy, Elsevier publications, doi:10.1016/j.foodpol.2010.11.026

Rubenito M. Lampayana, Roderick M. Rejesus, Grant R. Singleton, Bas A.M. Bouman, (2014), Adoption and economics of alternate wetting and drying water management for irrigated lowland rice, *Field Crops Research* 170 (2015) 95–108, Elsevier publications, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2014.10.013>

Majumder S, Bala BK, Arshad FM, Haque MA, Hossain MA. 2016. Food security through increasing technical efficiency and reducing postharvest losses of rice production systems in Bangladesh. *Food Security* 8(2): 361-374.

Ministry of Environment and Forests (MOEF), Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh. Intended Nationally Determined Contributions. September 2015: http://www4.unfccc.int/submissions/INDC/Published%20Documents/Bangladesh/1/INDC_2015_of_Bangladesh.pdf.

Palis, F.G., Lampayan, R.M., Bouman, B.A.M., 2014. Adoption and dissemination of alternate wetting and drying technology for boro rice cultivation in Bangladesh. In: Kumar, A., et al. (Eds.), *Mitigating Water-Shortage Challenges in Rice Cultivation: Aerobic and Alternate Wetting and Drying Rice Water-Saving Technologies*. IRRI and Asian Development Bank, Manila.

Priya Lal Chandra Paul, M.A. Rashid, Mousumi Paul, (2013), Refinement of Alternate Wetting and Drying Irrigation Method for Rice Cultivation, *Bangladesh Rice J.* 17(1&2): 33-37, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3329/brj.v17i1-2.20899>

Qureshi, A.S., Ahmed, Z., Krupnik, T.J., 2014. Groundwater management in Bangladesh: An analysis of problems and opportunities. Cereal Systems Initiative for South Asia Mechanization and Irrigation (CSISA-MI) Project, Research Report No. 2., Dhaka, Bangladesh: CIMMYT.

Rijsberman, F. R. 2006. Water Scarcity : Fact of fiction. *Agricultural Water Management* 80:5-22

SAIC (SAARC Agriculture Information Centre), 2007. IRRI develops technology for producing irrigated rice with less water. SAIC Newsletter. A Quarterly Publication of SAARC Agriculture Centre. Vol. 17:2.No. 2. PP.4-6.

UN Population Division (2012). World Population Prospects: The 2012 Revision, Volume I, Comprehensive Tables. Available at http://esa.un.org/unpd/wpp/Documentation/pdf/WPP2012_Volume-I_Comprehensive-Tables.pdf Accessed Nov 2014.

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. World Population Prospects: The 2015 Revision. (Medium variant)

World Bank. 2014. *Agricultural insurance in Bangladesh: promoting access to small and marginal farmers*. Washington, DC: USA

World Resources Institute Climate Analysis Indicators Tool (WRI CAIT) 2.0, 2015.